

3D SIMULATION OF FACE/CORE DEBOND PROPAGATION IN SANDWICH COMPOSITES EXPOSED TO CYCLIC LOADING

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Abstract

In this study a numerical routine to simulate fatigue debond propagation in sandwich panels is developed and implemented in the commercial finite element program ANSYS. To accelerate the crack growth simulation, a cycle jump method is utilized and implemented in the finite element routine. The proposed method (the cycle jump method) is based on conducting finite element analysis for a set of cycles to establish a trend line, extrapolating the trend line spanning many cycles, and use the extrapolated state as initial state for additional finite element simulations. Using the developed routine, 3D fatigue debond propagation in sandwich panels with elliptical and circular debond shape is simulated.

Methodology and numerical modeling

Sandwich composites are receiving increasing attention in a variety of weight critical applications like airplanes, wind turbine blades and ships due to their high stiffness/strength to weight ratio. However these structures are prone to different damages. Face/core debonding due to manufacturing flaws or in service overloading is among the most critical damages in sandwich structures, as the basic sandwich principle is compromised resulting in a lack of structural integrity and reliability. Design against debond fatigue failure in sandwich composites is associated with many challenges due to the complexity of the interface fracture problem. Typically, in order to study the response of a layered structure exposed to fatigue loading, experiments are conducted on both intact specimens and on specimens with a pre-existing interface cracks. In recent years few experimental studies on the face/core fatigue debond growth in sandwich composites, have been reported in the literature [1, 2]. Due to the difficulties and expenses associated

with conducting fatigue experiments, studies have been conducted recently to simulate crack growth in layered structures using numerical methods [3, 4]. However, the mentioned studies are all limited to 2D problems and few cycles due to the need for a high density mesh at the crack tip. To overcome this problem the authors proposed a new method (cycle jump method) to accelerate fatigue crack growth simulation in layered structures [5]. They showed that using the cycle jump method up to 80% reduction in computation time can be achieved with a fair accuracy [5]. The proposed method is based on conducting finite element analysis for a set of cycles to establish a trend line, extrapolating the trend line spanning many cycles, and use the extrapolated state as initial state for additional finite element simulations, see Figure 1. For the comprehensiveness of the paper a short summary of the cycle jump method is presented here.

Assuming that a FE analysis has been conducted for at least three computed load cycles, see Figure 2, for each state variable monitored, $y=y(t)$, where t is time, the discrete slope can be defined for every two adjacent cycles as [5]

$$S_{12}(t_2) = \frac{y(t_2) - y(t_1)}{\Delta t_{cyc}} \quad (1)$$

$$S_{23}(t_3) = \frac{y(t_3) - y(t_2)}{\Delta t_{cyc}} \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta t_{cyc} = t_2 - t_1 = t_3 - t_2$ is the time of each cycle.

The parameter q_y is introduced as the maximum relative error to control the accuracy of the simulation by using the following criterion

$$\left| \frac{S_{jump}(t_3 + \Delta t_{y,jump}) - S_{23}(t_3)}{S_{23}(t_3)} \right| \leq q_y \quad (3)$$

where q_y is the maximum allowed relative error, $\Delta t_{y, jump}$ the number of jumped cycles and S_{jump} is the estimated slope after the jump using linear extrapolation given by

$$S_{jump}(t_3 + \Delta t_{y, jump}) = S_{23}(t_3) + \frac{S_{23}(t_3) - S_{12}(t_2)}{\Delta t_{cyc}} \Delta t_{y, jump} \quad (4)$$

The control parameter ensures that the slope of the increment of the variable y after the cycle jump is “close enough” to its slope before the jump. q_y is specified by the user for each state parameters such as deflection or material properties. The allowed jump for each extrapolated parameter is determined by

$$\Delta t_{y, jump} = q_y \Delta t_{cyc} \frac{|S_{23}(t_3)|}{|S_{23}(t_3) - S_{12}(t_2)|} \quad (5)$$

Since the jump is determined for a set of state variables, the allowed jump Δt_{jump} is chosen as the minimum of the computed allowed jump times for each variable. The extrapolated state variables after each jump are determined by Heun integrator as

$$y(t_3 + \Delta t_{jump}) = y(t_3) + S_{23}(t_3) \Delta t_{jump} + A \quad (6)$$

$$A = [S_{23}(t_3) - S_{12}(t_2)] \frac{(\Delta t_{jump})^2}{2 \Delta t_{cyc}}$$

For more details about the cycle jump method see [5, 6]. In this study exploiting the cycle jump method, 3D fatigue debond propagation in sandwich panels with face/core debonds is simulated. The energy release rate and mode-mixity phase angle are chosen as state variables. To study the effect of debond geometry, panels with different elliptical debond shapes are analyzed. The sandwich panels are fully constrained in all four edges and the center of the debond is pulled by a cyclic load. Due to geometry and loading symmetry only a quarter panel is modeled, see Figure 3. After the mesh refinement convergence analysis the minimum element edge length $2e-5$ m at the crack tip is chosen for the simulation. To propagate the debond in each cycle, the strain energy release rate and mode-mixity phase angle are determined at different points along the debond front. The number of points can be arbitrarily defined. Once the strain energy release

rate and mode-mixity phase angle are determined for each point, using the crack growth rate as a function of energy release rate for discrete mode-mixities as input for the routine, the debond growth in each point can be evaluated. The new debond geometry following the debond growth is updated using a re-meshing algorithm. Strain energy release rate, G , and mode-mixity phase angle, ψ , are determined from relative nodal pair displacements, obtained from the finite element analysis using the CSDE method [7]. The energy release rate and the related phase angle are given by

$$G = \frac{\pi(1 + 4\varepsilon^2)}{8H_{11}x} \left(\frac{H_{11}}{H_{22}} \delta_y^2 + \delta_x^2 \right) \quad (7)$$

$$\psi = \tan^{-1} \left(\sqrt{\frac{H_{22} \delta_x}{H_{11} \delta_y}} \right) - \varepsilon \ln \left(\frac{x}{h} \right) + \tan^{-1}(2\varepsilon) \quad (8)$$

where δ_y and δ_x are the opening and sliding relative displacement of the crack flanks, H_{11} , H_{22} and the oscillatory index ε are bi-material constants determined from the elastic stiffnesses of the face and core, see Appendix A. h is the characteristic length of the crack problem. h has no direct physical meaning. Thus, it is here arbitrarily chosen as the face sheet thickness.

Debonded sandwich panels consisting of 2 mm thick plain weave E-glass/polyester face sheets over a 50 mm thick Divinycell H45 PVC foam are considered for the simulation. Face sheet and core material properties are listed in Table 1. The debonded panels are square of 310 mm length. An elliptical face/core debond with the short radius b of 45 mm and large radius a of 76.5 mm is created at the center of the panel. 8-noded iso-parametric brick elements (SOLID45) are used in the finite element model. Due to the current lack of suitable experimental fatigue crack growth rate data, for simplicity the crack growth rate vs. strain energy release rate is assumed constant for mode-mixity phase angles larger and smaller than -10 degrees and chosen arbitrarily as

$$\frac{da}{dN} = 0.000005 \Delta G^2 \quad \text{for} \quad |\Psi| < 10^\circ \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{da}{dN} = 0.000002 \Delta G^2 \quad \text{for} \quad |\Psi| > 10^\circ \quad (10)$$

where ΔG is the difference between maximum and minimum strain energy release rate in each cycle and da/dN is the crack growth rate. The simulation is conducted in force control with the maximum amplitude of 0.35 kN and loading ratio of 0.1.

Results and discussions

To investigate the distribution of the strain energy release rate and mode-mixity phase angle along the debond front, radar diagrams are shown in Figures 4 and 5 from the static analysis of the debonded panels exposed to maximum applied fatigue load. Debonded panels with short radius of 45 mm and ratio of large radius/short radius a/b of 1.7, 1.4 and 1.1 are analyzed. In the diagrams zero and ninety degrees correspond to the points on the debond front on short and large radiuses of the ellipse respectively. Maximum energy release rate and mode-mixity occur at the point on the short ellipse radius because of the small crack length and decreases toward the larger radius. As the ratio a/b decreases to one (circle) distribution of both G and mode-mixity become more even as expected. To evaluate the accuracy of the implemented cycle jump method, fatigue debond propagation simulation was conducted for 500 cycles. To study the effect of the control parameter on the accuracy and computational efficiency of simulation, simulations with different control parameters, q_ψ , were conducted. A reference simulation, simulating all individual cycles was performed to verify the accuracy of the simulations using the cycle jump method. Figures 6 shows the deflection of the loading point (“Z deflection”) as a function of cycles for the reference simulation and the cycle jump simulation with control parameters $q_G=q_\psi=2.5$. It can be seen that the evaluated deflections from the cycle jump method show a good agreement with the reference simulation. Using the control parameter 2.5 the cycle jump method simulation requires 171 cycles to simulate 500 cycles, resulting in 66% reduction in the computation time with a fair accuracy. Debond growth at three locations along the debond front is shown in Figure 6 from the reference simulation and simulations exploiting the cycle jump method with the control parameters $q_G=q_\psi=2.5$. At all locations the cycle jump simulation estimates the debond growth with a fair accuracy. To measure the computational efficiency

of the cycle jump method for different control parameters, the ratio R is introduced:

$$R = \frac{N_{jump}}{N_{ref}} \quad (11)$$

where N_{jump} is the number of jumped cycles and N_{ref} is the total number of cycles in the reference simulation. To measure the accuracy of the simulations the relative error is defined as:

$$Er = \left| \frac{y_{ref} - y_{jump}}{y_{ref}} \right| \times 100 \quad (12)$$

where y_{ref} and y_{jump} are the measured parameters from the reference and cycle jump analysis respectively. The overall average error of the cycle jump method is evaluated as

$$\overline{Er} = \frac{\sum_N Er}{N} \quad (13)$$

where N is number of simulated cycles and Er is the average error of each cycle. Number of jumped cycles, computational efficiency and average relative error for the debond growth for simulations with different control parameters are listed in Table 2. Increasing the control parameter the number of simulated cycles decreases significantly, but the accuracy of the simulation decreases as well. Nevertheless the average error in the evaluation of the debond length is less than 0.1% for all control parameters. It can be seen that for $q_G=q_\psi=4$ with a good accuracy using the cycle jump method, only 145 cycles are required for the simulation of 500 cycles, resulting in 71% reduction in the computation time. Fatigue debond growth is simulated for 2500 cycles using the control parameter $q_G=q_\psi=4$ and a/b ratio of 1.7, 1.4, 1.1 and 1.0. Figures 8 shows the debond radius at different locations along the elliptical debond front with a/b ratio of 1.7 vs. cycles. During the initial cycles the debond growth is very small close to the large radius of ellipse, but as the debond propagates the radius of different points along debond front converges showing a change in the debond shape from ellipse to circle. The number of simulation cycles and computational efficiency of the simulations are shown in Table 3. By exploiting the cycle jump

method, around 80% reduction in computation time is achieved. It can be seen that despite using the same control parameter, the number of simulated cycles are different for panels with different debond a/b ratio due to different behavior of state parameters (energy release rate and phase angle) in each case.

Conclusion

A method for the accelerated simulation of 3D fatigue debond growth in sandwich components was presented. To accelerate the simulation a cycle jump method was exploited. The proposed cycle jump method is based on conducting finite element analysis for a set of cycles to establish a trend line, extrapolating the trend line spanning many cycles, and use the extrapolated state as an initial state for additional finite element simulations. Using the developed method fatigue debond propagation in the sandwich panels with an elliptical face/core debond in the center of the panels was simulated. To examine the accuracy and computational efficiency of the developed method, a reference simulation, simulating all individual cycle and simulations exploiting the cycle jump method with different control parameters were conducted. It was shown that with a good accuracy (around 0.1% error in the debond length) using the cycle jump method more than 70% reduction in the computation time can be achieved. Finally debonded panels with different elliptical shape were simulated for 2500 cycles exploiting the cycle jump method.

Table 1: Face and core material properties [5]

Material	E (MPa)	G (MPa)	ν
Face sheet	16400	6300	0.31
Core: H45	50	15	0.32

Table 2: Computational efficiency and average relative error for the crack length

Control parameter $q_G=q_\psi$	Number of simulated cycles	Number of jumps occurred	R	Average error of crack length (%)
1	303	16	0.39	0.03
2.5	171	17	0.66	0.05
4	145	15	0.71	0.08

a/b	Number of simulated cycles	R
1.7	588	0.77
1.4	376	0.85
1.1	288	0.89
1	415	0.83

Table 3: Number of jumped cycles and computational efficiency for the simulations with control parameter $q_G=q_\psi=4$ for 2500 cycles

Fig.1. Schematic representation of the cycle jump method

Fig.2. Extrapolation scheme of the cycle jump method

Fig.3. Finite element model of the quarter panel with an elliptical debond in the center

Fig.4. Distribution of the energy release rate in the debond front

Fig.5. Distribution of the mode-mixity phase angle in the debond front

Fig.6. Deflection of the loading point (“Z deflection”) from reference analysis and the cycle jump simulation vs. cycles

Fig.7. Crack length at different crack front points from reference analysis and cycle jump simulation vs. cycles

Fig.8. Debond radius vs. cycle for sandwich panels with elliptical debond with a/b ratio of a/b=1.7 for 2500 cycles

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Appendix A

H_{11} and H_{22} , introduced in Equations (7) and (8), are bimaterial constants, depending on material compliances [7]:

$$H_{11} = \left[2n\lambda^{1/4} \sqrt{S_{11}S_{22}} \right]_1 + \left[2n\lambda^{1/4} \sqrt{S_{11}S_{22}} \right]_2 \quad (A1)$$

$$H_{22} = \left[2n\lambda^{-1/4} \sqrt{S_{11}S_{22}} \right]_1 + \left[2n\lambda^{-1/4} \sqrt{S_{11}S_{22}} \right]_2 \quad (A2)$$

λ and n are non-dimensional orthotropic constants given in terms of the elements S_{11} and S_{22} of the compliance matrix:

$$\lambda = \frac{S_{11}}{S_{22}} \quad (A3)$$

$$n = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(1 + \rho)} \quad \rho = \frac{1}{2} \frac{2S_{12} + S_{66}}{\sqrt{S_{11}S_{22}}}$$

The compliance elements for plane stress conditions are given by

$$S_{11} = \frac{1}{E_1} \quad S_{12} = S_{21} = -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} = -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_2} \quad (A4)$$

$$S_{22} = \frac{1}{E_2} \quad S_{66} = \frac{1}{G_{12}}$$

For plane strain conditions,

$$S_{ij}^* = S_{ij} - \frac{S_{i3}S_{j3}}{S_{33}} \quad (A5)$$

The oscillatory index, ε , in equations (7) and (8) is given as

$$\varepsilon = \frac{1}{2\pi} \ln\left(\frac{1-\beta}{1+\beta}\right) \quad (A6)$$

where

$$\beta = \frac{\left[S_{12} + \sqrt{S_{11}S_{22}} \right]_2 - \left[S_{12} + \sqrt{S_{11}S_{22}} \right]_1}{\sqrt{H_{11}H_{22}}} \quad (A7)$$